

Delivering Demand Response Services to the Power Grid via Smart Building Load Flexibility

November 2025

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the funding support provided by RMIT University and The Hong Kong Polytechnic University (PolyU) to produce this white paper. This paper was developed as part of the PolyU–RMIT FutureLab (FutureLab) project.

This white paper was typeset using \LaTeX .

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons CC BY License. This licence allows reusers to distribute, remix, adapt and build upon the material in any medium or format, so long as attribution is given to the creator. The licence allows for commercial use. To view a copy of the license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/about/ccllicenses>.

Preferred Citation: J.S. Bryant, H. Li, N. Maheepala, L. Meegahapola, S. Wang, L. Wang, F. Xiao, R. Yang, S. Bu, D. Robert, Z. Xu, A. Vahidnia, and S. Yan, “Delivering Demand Response Services to the Power Grid via Smart Building Load Flexibility,” Ver. 2, Nov. 2025.

For further information on FutureLab, please visit:

- <https://www.rmit.edu.au/news/all-news/2024/sep/futurelab-launch>
- <https://www.polyu.edu.hk/pair/publications/issue-12/ne01---pair-and-stem-college-of-rmit-university-establish-polyu-rmit-futurelab/>

Contact:

- Professor Lasantha Meegahapola (lasantha.meegahapola@rmit.edu.au)
- Professor Shengwei Wang (shengwei.wang@polyu.edu.hk)

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14571315](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14571315)

Contents

Executive Summary	1
1 Introduction	3
1.1 Technical background of power systems' evolution	3
1.2 The importance of power system frequency support	4
1.3 Demand response and smart building participation potential	6
2 Building Energy Characterisation and Flexibility	8
2.1 Sources of building energy flexibility	9
2.2 Characterisation of building load flexibility	10
2.3 Building load flexibility opportunities and challenges	12
2.3.1 Opportunities	12
2.3.2 Challenges	13
3 Power Grid Support Services	13
3.1 The Australian context	13
3.1.1 Frequency Control Ancillary Services	15
3.1.2 Demand response initiatives	15
3.2 The Hong Kong and Mainland China context	17
3.2.1 Power system ancillary services	18
3.2.2 Demand response initiatives	20
4 Technologies and Strategies to Drive Building Energy Efficiency and Grid Support Services	21
4.1 Smart sensors	21
4.2 Smart loads and inverters	22
4.3 Artificial intelligence and machine learning	23
4.4 Retrofit strategies for energy-efficient buildings	24
4.4.1 Retrofitting Leading to Energy Efficiency, Energy Flexibility, and Grid Support Services	25
4.4.2 Barriers and Future Considerations	25
4.5 Building material advancements	27

5	Opportunities to Support the Grid via Building Loads	28
5.1	Capability and applicability of building load flexibility for different grid storage needs	28
5.2	Applicability of building load flexibility for current ancillary services . . .	29
5.3	Potential opportunities of building load flexibility for power grid balancing	29
5.4	Barriers to building load flexibility adoption and deployment	30
6	Regulatory and Policy Landscapes	30
6.1	The Australian context	30
6.1.1	AS/NZS 4755.1:2017 - Demand Response Capabilities and Supporting Technologies for Electrical Products	32
6.1.2	Green Star Buildings	32
6.1.3	Other rating systems and provisions	33
6.2	The Hong Kong and Mainland China context	33
7	Future Research and Industry Questions	34
7.1	Open industry questions	35
7.2	Open research questions	35
8	Conclusion	35
9	References	36

List of Figures

1	Installed inverter-connected renewable energy capacity worldwide from 2010 to 2050 under various decarbonisation scenarios	5
2	Illustrative power system frequency and demand response dynamics	7
3	Characterisation of load flexibility	8
4	Illustrative load flexibility versus percentage of total building load	12
5	Australia's eastern seaboard electricity system	14
6	Current Frequency Control Ancillary Service market structure in Australia	16
7	Ancillary service categories in Mainland China	19
8	Framework linking building retrofitting, efficiency, flexibility, and grid support services	26
9	Barriers and future considerations for building retrofits aiming energy efficiency	27

Nomenclature

Acronyms / Abbreviations

AC	Alternating current
AEMC	Australian Energy Market Commission
AEMO	Australian Energy Market Operator
AI	Artificial intelligence
ARENA	Australian Renewable Energy Agency
AS/NZS	Australian/New Zealand Standards
BESS	Battery energy storage system
CCHP	Combined cooling, heating, and power
CHP	Combined heat and power
COAG EC	Council of Australian Governments Energy Council
EMS	Energy management system
ESB	Energy Security Board
EV	Electric vehicle
FCAS	Frequency Control Ancillary Services
GW	Gigawatt
HVAC	Heating, ventilation, and air-conditioning
IBR	Inverter-based resource
IoT	Internet of Things
kVA	Kilovolt-amperes
LCA	Life-Cycle Assessment

ML	Machine learning
MWh	Megawatt-hour
MW	Megawatt
NatHERS	Nationwide House Energy Rating Scheme
NCC	National Construction Code
NEM	National Electricity Market
NSW	New South Wales
PV	Photovoltaic
QLD	Queensland
RERT	Reliability and Emergency Reserve Trader
SA	South Australia
TAS	Tasmania
US	United States
V2G	Vehicle-to-grid
VIC	Victoria

Executive Summary

Power systems worldwide face stability challenges as renewable energy integration transforms electricity networks. Renewable energy sources' fundamentally different operation, intermittency, and physics versus traditional synchronous generators primarily drive these challenges.

Ancillary services, traditionally delivered by synchronous generators as a by-product of electricity production, help keep power system voltage and frequency within bounds. However, renewable energy sources can complicate their provision. Demand response is a power balancing method that encourages customers to adjust their energy usage in response to price signals. Buildings are particularly attractive participants owing to their significant energy consumption and high flexibility in energy control. Digitalisation and advances in communications technologies, artificial intelligence, and machine learning enhance buildings' potential for demand response provision.

This paper explores demand response service provision via smart building load flexibility. We show how building energy flexibility can be characterised by power adjustment direction, capacity, availability, predictability, and response time. Key flexibility sources include shiftable loads like electric vehicles, non-shiftable loads such as lighting, and controllable loads like heating and ventilation. Electric vehicles—particularly those with vehicle-to-grid technology—and heating, ventilation, and cooling systems are the most attractive building loads for demand response owing to their flexibility, response time, and duration.

We also analyse ancillary service frameworks in Australia, Hong Kong, and Mainland China. Australia's well-established market supports demand response projects like vehicle-to-grid initiatives. Hong Kong and Mainland China are in earlier development stages, with opportunities for modernisation and expanded market frameworks.

Promising technologies for enhancing grid support include smart sensors, loads and inverters, as well as artificial intelligence. They can help optimise building energy management, facilitate real-time control, and provide predictive capabilities from historical data. Solar façades may also help buildings participate more in grid service provision, while advanced building insulation materials can help improve energy efficiency. Moreover, building retrofitting strategies also directly and indirectly contribute to energy flexibility aspects of the buildings, and hence their importance is emphasised in the paper.

The paper concludes by examining the regulatory and policy landscapes across Australia, Hong Kong, and Mainland China and posing open industry and research questions. In Australia, reform has sought to drive greater flexibility, reform trader services, and provide fit-for-purpose consumer protections. Meanwhile, Mainland China is implementing more demand-side management measures, guidelines, and policies to enhance energy efficiency and grid stability through demand response uptake. Hong Kong has only implemented a few demand-side management measures—it has yet to fully develop direct regulations or policies addressing building load flexibility engagement in grid support ancillary services. Effective regulations, policies, and market mechanisms will be critical for unlocking building load flexibility.

Overall, advancements in electric vehicles, artificial intelligence, smart energy conversion, and digitalisation provide substantial opportunities for leveraging smart building load flexibility for demand response services to power grids.

1 Introduction

Global warming concerns have catalysed a paradigm shift in power systems worldwide by helping drive decarbonising technological innovation. Consequently, renewable energy sources like wind and solar photovoltaic (PV) systems are increasingly displacing traditional coal- and gas-fired synchronous generation. Power electronic inverters interface these sources with the power system, efficiently converting their electrical energy into a suitable form and controlling them according to technical requirements. Hence, we typically refer to solar and wind generators as inverter-based resources (IBRs).

Meanwhile, buildings play a pivotal role in addressing global warming, accounting for a significant portion of global energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions. Implementing environmentally friendly technologies, introducing smart energy management systems, and improving insulation can enhance buildings' energy efficiency, reducing their carbon footprint. Moreover, leveraging demand flexibility in buildings by dynamically adjusting energy usage in response to grid conditions can reduce peak demand, facilitate greater renewable energy integration, and improve power system stability and reliability. The interplay between building energy consumption, demand-side management measures, and the evolving power system presents a significant opportunity for urban infrastructure to aid global efforts in combating climate change.

1.1 Technical background of power systems' evolution

IBRs fundamentally differ from traditional synchronous generators, augmenting power systems' behaviour. The most significant differences include:

1. **Operating principle:** Synchronous generators couple directly to the power system and comprise large rotating masses that contain inertia. As a result, their rotational speed varies proportionally to the power system frequency, and their inertia helps stabilise the system by opposing speed changes. Conversely, IBRs interface with the power system through the inverter and do not inherently contain inertia [1].
2. **Intermittency:** Synchronous generators have a constant fuel source, such as coal or natural gas, and are dispatchable. In contrast, wind and solar resources are inherently intermittent. The sun does not always shine, and the wind does not

always blow. Hence, IBRs' power output fluctuates temporally [2].

3. **Physics:** While physical machine characteristics determine synchronous generator behaviour, software-defined control loops govern IBR behaviour [3]. IBRs' software-defined nature provides significant behavioural flexibility and (typically) much faster responses to power system changes than synchronous generators.

Additionally, power systems' overall generation is becoming more distributed. For example, rooftop solar PV (distributed generation) is now widely found in distribution systems. This new generation changes the nature of power flows from unidirectional (high-voltage transmission network to low-voltage distribution system) to bidirectional (occurring in both directions). These differences and augmentations make controlling and operating power systems harder, particularly as the IBR penetration increases.

Figure 1 illustrates the current and projected installed generation capacity for solar and wind systems worldwide considering three (3) decarbonisation scenarios: Stated Policies, Announced Pledges, and Net Zero Emissions by 2050 [4], [5]. The Stated Policies scenario considers the latest policy settings. In contrast, the Announced Pledges scenario assumes we meet all national energy and climate targets governments make. Moreover, the Net Zero Emissions by 2050 scenario considers global warming limited to 1.5°C. Under each scenario, the combined solar PV and wind share by 2050 as a percentage of total installed generation capacity is expected to be 64%, 68% and 71%, respectively [5]. Hence, we will require novel strategies for controlling and operating power systems with such high penetrations of IBRs.

1.2 The importance of power system frequency support

Power system frequency corresponds to the number of cycles per second in the alternating current (AC) waveform. Frequency increases if the total generation exceeds the total demand (load). Conversely, the frequency decreases if the total demand exceeds the total generation. Therefore, we can think of power system frequency as a barometer for how balanced generation and demand are at any instant. Instantaneously matching power system generation and demand is thus crucial for maintaining a stable power system frequency (and overall power system stability) [6].

Renewable energy sources can challenge this balance. For example, solar resources' peak

Figure 1: Installed inverter-connected renewable energy capacity worldwide from 2010 to 2050 under various decarbonisation pathways. (a) Solar photovoltaic. (b) Wind.

generation output typically occurs at midday, which (generally) coincides with minimum demand. Likewise, wind fluctuates throughout the day, which can alter wind farms' power output. Moreover, as these IBRs displace synchronous generators across the system, there is inherently less inertia, which makes the power system frequency more dynamic—minor changes in load or generation lead to more significant frequency changes—and the frequency stability more fragile.

We can alter the generation-demand balance at the transmission level (through generators connected to the high-voltage transmission network) or the distribution level (using the loads and distributed generation of buildings and households). Some contemporary frequency regulation strategies at the transmission level include:

- **Grid-scale battery energy storage system (BESS) deployment:** BESSs can absorb or inject power swiftly to counteract demand-generation imbalances [7]. Their fast-acting responses benefit low-inertia systems with dynamic frequency behaviour.
- **Advanced control for wind farms:** Involves using multiple inverter control loops to facilitate extraction of wind turbine inertia [8]. Active power curtailment and inertia emulation are two main advanced control methods.

- **Deloading solar farms:** Involves intentionally operating below the maximum power output, leaving enough power reserve to respond to under-frequency events [9]. This option involves receiving less remuneration from wholesale electricity market participation but (hopefully) recouping this by participating in frequency control ancillary service markets.

1.3 Demand response and smart building participation potential

Demand response, which involves customers voluntarily reducing or shifting their electricity usage, typically in response to pricing or incentives, is a method at the distribution level to help maintain the generation-demand balance [10], [11].

Figure 2 illustrates how demand response activates to help stabilise frequency and balance the power system's total demand and generation. An over-frequency scenario is when the power system frequency exceeds a threshold above the standard value. In this case, demand response arrests the frequency increase by increasing the load consumption. Conversely, load consumption decreases for an under-frequency scenario where the power system frequency drops below a threshold less than the standard value.

We can generate revenue from these responses by helping support the grid, leading to many demand response opportunities.

In Australia, about 25% of total electricity usage is from non-residential commercial buildings¹ [12] and around 24% from residential buildings, such as houses and apartments [13].² As large electricity consumers, buildings present a promising opportunity for providing support services to power grids.

The increasing digitisation of the modern world and advances in communications technologies, artificial intelligence, machine learning, and data analytics further bolster the possibility of leveraging load flexibility in smart buildings to deliver demand response services harmoniously.

This paper systematically examines load flexibility and demand response from smart

¹For example, offices, restaurants, industrial premises, shops, hotels, schools, and hospitals.

²Australia's most recent census data (2021) counted 10,852,208 private dwellings, with 70% being separate houses, 13% townhouses and 16% apartments.

Figure 2: Illustrative power system frequency and demand response dynamics.

buildings. We also discuss some technologies and opportunities for grid support service provision via building loads and identify open questions from academic and industry perspectives.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 examines buildings' energy characterisation and flexibility. Section 3 discusses power grid support services, particularly in Australia, Hong Kong, and Mainland China. Then, Section 4 examines some promising technologies we could leverage when providing grid support services from smart buildings. Section 5 summarises the latest research and explains the barriers and opportunities for grid support service provision from smart buildings. Section 6 looks at regulatory and policy aspects. Section 7 lists some open questions from academic and industry perspectives. Last, Section 8 concludes the paper.

2 Building Energy Characterisation and Flexibility

A building's energy flexibility relates to its ability to manage its demand and generation according to local climate conditions, user needs, and grid requirements [14]. Thus, a balance exists between the best interests of end-users and the power grid.

At the heart of these requirements are the electric loads found throughout buildings. Load flexibility relates to power adjustments sustained over a given duration to balance supply and demand at an instant in time [15]. Figure 3 characterises these power adjustments by [16]:

1. The **direction** that describes a flexible resource's response. Some resources can only provide downward responses (i.e., unidirectional). Others can deliver upward and downward responses (i.e., bidirectional).
2. The **electrical capacity** that characterises a resource's power adjustment magnitude. Two main categories emerge when considering the **time duration** of adjustments. The first category relates to resources that can sustain significant power adjustments over short periods. The second corresponds to those that can sustain

Figure 3: Characterisation of load flexibility.

more modest adjustments over longer periods.

3. A resource's **availability** (defined by **starting time**) and **predictability**, given that some loads may only be available during certain times of the day either due to their nature or end-user behaviour.
4. The **response time** that corresponds to how quickly a resource can respond to a demand response signal.

These characteristics are critical to evaluating whether a load is suitable for providing a demand response to support the grid (or how best it can deliver grid support).

2.1 Sources of building energy flexibility

Three (3) main categories of building energy flexibility exist [14]. These are shiftable loads, non-shiftable loads, and other controllable loads. **Shiftable loads** can be interrupted or rescheduled to exploit cheaper off-peak hours, reducing peak demand with minimal impact on end-users. Their flexibility primarily relates to timing, with a fixed total energy consumption. Examples include washing machines, dishwashers, charging devices, and electric vehicles.

Non-shiftable loads are inflexible with energy consumption profiles that cannot be modified regardless of the system's energy cost and volume. Lighting, cooking, and televisions fall into this category.

Last, there are **other controllable loads** that are both shiftable and adjustable—we can modify their energy consumption using optimal control strategies like fan speed control, dimming, or thermostatic control. Adjusting total energy use and consumption patterns can help optimise for peak periods or cost savings. These loads include heating, ventilation, and air-conditioning (HVAC) systems, non-essential lighting, and water heaters.

Thus, the main sources of electrical load flexibility in buildings include:

1. Electric vehicles (EVs)³

³Including those with vehicle-to-grid (V2G) technology, which, in addition to battery charging, allows a vehicle's battery to discharge and provide services to the grid.

2. Battery energy storage systems (BESSs)
3. Electric water heaters
4. HVAC systems⁴
5. Scheduled loads, such as appliances, e.g., dishwashers and washing machines
6. Refrigerators
7. Lighting

2.2 Characterisation of building load flexibility

Table 1 provides a detailed breakdown of various building loads' flexibility [16]. EVs (with V2G technology) and BESSs provide the most directional flexibility since they can deliver bidirectional (upward and downward) responses and are capable of acting as prosumers, i.e., behaving as a generator and a load (at different times). They are also equipped with the quickest response speeds, and depending on their design, can provide long-duration responses with modest magnitudes (energy) or short-duration responses with larger magnitudes (capacity). Currently, EVs and BESSs may not be abundant within buildings owing to their capital costs and infrastructure challenges. However, both are likely to have significant growth in the future.

HVAC systems are highly available and are abundant in almost all buildings. They can provide bidirectional responses, while their response speed depends on the adopted control strategy. Their response duration depends on the thermal characteristics of the building envelope and air-conditioning system, the thermal comfort constraints, and the power capacity requested. Thus, different responses may be provided based on the design. Meanwhile, domestic hot water systems have fast response speeds with high availability and predictability. Like HVAC systems, refrigerators are also commonly found in domestic settings. They are characterised by fast response speeds, high availability and predictability, and response durations over minutes.

⁴HVAC systems may be broken down further into standard heaters (with only heating functionality), standard air conditioning units (with only cooling functionality), and reverse cycle air conditioning units (split systems with integrated heating and cooling functionality).

Table 1: Characterisation of different residential loads and their flexibility.

Appliance Type	Storable Appliances					Non-Storable Appliances		
						Shiftable Appliances	Non-Shiftable Appliances	
							Curtable	Non-Curtable
Flexibility Characteristics	Electric Vehicles	Battery Storage	Heating & Cooling	Domestic Hot Water	Refrigerators	Wet Appliances & Dryers	Non-Essential Lighting	Cooking & 'Must Use' Home Devices
Interruptible	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No ^a	Yes ^b	No
Capacity or Energy Type^c	Both	Both	Both ^d	Both	Capacity	Capacity	Depends ^e	-
Prosumer Capability^f	Prosumer ^g	Prosumer	Consumer	Consumer	Consumer	Consumer	Consumer	-
Response Direction^h	Bidirectional	Bidirectional	Bidirectional	Unidirectional	Unidirectional	Unidirectional	Bidirectional	-
Response Speed	Quick	Quick	Depends	Fast	Fast	Moderate	Quick	-
Response Duration	Hours	Hours	Depends	Hours	Minutes	Minutes	Hours	-
Response Magnitude	Large	Large	Medium	Medium	Small	Small/Medium	Small	-
Availability	Evening & night	Always	Often	Often	Always	Rarely	Evening	-
Predictability	High	Perfect	High	High	High	Moderate	Good	-

^a Wet appliances such as washing machines are interruptible for up to a few minutes.

^b Interrupting lighting would only be used as a last resort in practice.

^c Relates to a load's energy/power ratio. A low ratio (capacity type) corresponds to high power output over a short time and is thus more suitable for ancillary services. A high ratio (energy type) relates to power provision over longer durations and is thus suited to longer applications, e.g., load levelling.

^d Depends on the control strategy adopted, which also affects the response speed.

^e Newer energy-efficient LED lighting is the energy type. Older, less efficient lighting is the power type.

^f If a resource is a "prosumer", it can produce and consume power at different times (i.e., bidirectional power flow corresponding to generator and load behaviour). A "consumer" can only act as a load (i.e., unidirectional power flow) and only consumes power.

^g With V2G technology, electric vehicles can respond in both directions.

^h Refers to a resource's response directional flexibility. Unidirectional means a resource can only provide a downward response. Bidirectional sources are capable of providing both upward and downward responses.

On the other hand, wet appliances and dryers have poorer availability, moderately fast response speeds, and moderate predictability. Non-essential lighting has good predictability, a quick response speed, and a response duration in the order of hours. However, such lighting is unlikely to be used in demand response programs since it is generally only a minor proportion of total lighting. Moreover, lighting consumes only a small load since it is energy efficient.

2.3 Building load flexibility opportunities and challenges

Given the various loads found throughout buildings, many opportunities and challenges exist for exploiting load flexibility.

2.3.1 Opportunities

Figure 4 illustrates estimated load flexibilities versus the percentage of total building load that each load consumes for future smart buildings. Given their abundance, power usage, and availability, exploiting HVAC systems' flexibility for demand response presents an

Figure 4: Illustrative estimated load flexibility versus percentage of total building load.

attractive opportunity. Moreover, the high flexibility of EVs, particularly those with V2G technology, will also become increasingly attractive as they become ubiquitous. Hot water systems constitute a large proportion of building load—and while they are less flexible compared to HVAC systems and EVs—their different characteristics may be beneficial for ensuring the provision of various types of demand responses. The “smart load” concept, which facilitates adaptive energy consumption, is designed around HVAC and hot water systems and could be further explored (refer to Section 4.2).

2.3.2 Challenges

It is worth noting that there are capital costs associated with installing infrastructure for BESSs and EVs in buildings, which could be challenging to navigate depending on the size of the battery system or the number of EVs. For example, in buildings like apartment blocks or shopping centres, significant EV charging points could necessitate upgrades to the existing electrical installation to cope with the additional power flows and load demand.

Technical challenges may also exist, such as a lack of effective methods and technologies to accurately predict and optimally control building load flexibility for effective grid support.

3 Power Grid Support Services

Power grid support services, also known as ancillary services, are designed to maintain power system stability by holding the electricity supply’s characteristics⁵ close to their designed (i.e., “nominal”) values [6]. We typically procure frequency-related ancillary services through market-based frameworks since the frequency is a system-wide issue⁶.

3.1 The Australian context

Australia’s electricity system comprises three separate electricity networks: 1) The eastern seaboard electricity system (also referred to as the National Electricity Market (NEM)),

⁵These characteristics relate to the AC voltage waveform’s magnitude and frequency.

⁶As opposed to the localised nature of voltage control, which we generally deal with contractually.

Figure 5: Australia's eastern seaboard electricity system.

2) Western Australia electricity network (also known as the Wholesale Electricity Market (WEM), and 3) Northern Territory electricity network. The eastern seaboard electricity system corresponds to the power system that spans the contiguous geographical states of Queensland (QLD), New South Wales (NSW), Victoria (VIC), and South Australia (SA), as well as Tasmania (TAS)—refer to Figure 5⁷. The maximum and minimum demand records correspond to 35,796 MW (29 January 2009) and 11,009 MW (29 October 2023), respectively [17]. While the system's average annual renewable energy contribution is around 40%, a new instantaneous renewable energy contribution record of 73.89% was set on 1 October 2024. Table 2 summarises the system's generation capacity.

⁷It must be noted that Western Australia and the Northern Territory have their own network operating under a different set of rules and regulations

Table 2: Australia’s eastern seaboard electricity system generation capacity [17].

Generation Type	Technology Type	Generation Capacity [%]	Generation Capacity [GW]
Thermal energy	Gas	14.4	12.244
	Coal	25	21.255
Renewable energy	Rooftop solar	24.7	21.000
	Wind	13.1	11.125
	Grid solar	10.7	9.130
	Hydro	9.4	7.999
	Battery storage	1.9	1.605
	Biomass/other	0.9	0.766

3.1.1 Frequency Control Ancillary Services

Power system frequency control in Australia’s national electricity system is currently served through a mature framework that consists of 10 (ten) services, which form the basis of the Frequency Control Ancillary Services (FCAS) market [18]. Figure 6 summarises the FCAS market structure.

The regulation market comprises raise and lower services designed to correct minor frequency deviations from small changes in load and generation. Meanwhile, the contingency market includes raise and lower services across various timescales: very fast (1-second), fast (6-second), slow (60-second), and delayed (5-minute). Contingency responses are designed to correct more significant power system frequency deviations caused by demand-generation imbalances. The response timescales correspond to the technology types found across the power system. For example, the fast and very fast markets are suited to swift BESS response capabilities.

Hence, these markets present opportunities for remuneration from the provision of responses across various timetables and response directions.

3.1.2 Demand response initiatives

Numerous demand response initiatives have been undertaken across Australia in recent years, and many projects are still underway. Some examples of these initiatives include:

- *AGL’s Demand Response Project* [19]:

Figure 6: Current FCAS market structure comprising regulation and contingency markets.

- 18 MW of demand response reserves deployed, increasing to 19 MW and 20 MW in years two and three, respectively.
- 17 MW came from commercial and industrial participants, with the remaining 3 MW from AGL’s residential customers in New South Wales.
- The reserves were delivered when called upon by the Australian Energy Market Operator (AEMO) under the Short Notice Reliability and Emergency Reserve Trader (RERT).
- EV charging was shown to have the potential to be a substantial controllable load that can be shaped and managed without adversely affecting vehicle amenities.
- *PLUS ES South Australia Demand Flexibility Trial*: utilising up to 20,000 existing smart meters to dynamically orchestrate hot water load [20].

- *Enel X Australia's Commercial Refrigeration Flexible Demand Project*: examining retail refrigeration (15.4 MW) as well as refrigerated warehouses (5.4 MW) [21].

Case Study I summarises the outcomes of a successful V2G deployment project in Australia's national electricity system.

Case Study I: V2G Deployment in the Australian Power System

The Australian Renewable Energy Agency's (ARENA's) *Realising Electric Vehicle-to-Grid Services* project, which ran from June 2020 to March 2023, sought to unlock the full economic and grid benefits of V2G services in Australia [22]. The project deployed a fleet of 51 V2G capable vehicles across the Australian Capital Territory, enabling the delivery of contingency Frequency Control Ancillary Services (FCAS) within Australia's National Electricity Market (NEM).

The project's main findings included:

1. The average EV could have earned approximately A\$12,000 participating in the New South Wales FCAS raise regulation market, or around A\$2,600 in the NSW FCAS raise 60-second contingency market, based on 2022 data.
2. The average EV could earn approximately A\$9,000 from participating in the New South Wales FCAS lower regulation market or around A\$2,000 from participating in the lower 60-second contingency market, based on 2022 data.
3. Vehicle charging behaviours affect remuneration significantly. For example, vehicles were often fully charged when FCAS were required. Hence, enough headroom (capacity to respond) must be left to participate in FCAS lower markets.
4. Participation in the contingency FCAS market is unlikely to impact driver experience and EV battery degradation significantly.

3.2 The Hong Kong and Mainland China context

Hong Kong's power system has an installed generation capacity of 11,670 MW—primarily natural gas (over 50%), coal, and nuclear energy imported from Mainland China [23].

Meanwhile, the maximum and minimum electricity demands are around 9,000 MW and 3,000 MW, respectively. The local renewable energy penetration is currently low (< 1%), which the government gradually plans to raise to 7.5-10% by 2035.

On the other hand, Mainland China has a significantly larger installed generation capacity of 3,263 GW with a maximum electricity demand of around 1,451 GW. Renewable energy like solar, wind, and hydro contributes to approximately 35.5% of the total annual electricity consumption, as shown in Table 3 [24].

3.2.1 Power system ancillary services

Hong Kong is significantly behind in establishing specific regulatory frameworks for ancillary services. The only ancillary services currently implemented are a demand charge pricing scheme based on the monthly maximum demand in kilovolt-amperes (kVA) and a peak demand management program aimed at encouraging bulk tariff or large power tariff customers to reduce power use during peak demand periods [25].

In contrast, Mainland China is in the early stages of developing a comprehensive ancillary services market. The government has recently accelerated market development by incorporating more services and engaging emerging market entities to facilitate the energy transition. The ancillary services market now operates within a systematic framework comprising three main categories: active power balancing, reactive power balancing, and contingency and restoration, as shown in Figure 7. Active power balancing involves services such as primary frequency control, secondary frequency control (automatic gener-

Table 3: Mainland China's national electricity system generation capacity.

Generation Type	Technology Type	Generation Capacity [%]	Generation Capacity [GW]
Thermal energy	Gas	7.6	249
	Coal	35.9	1,170
	Nuclear	1.8	58
Renewable energy	Wind	14.7	480
	Solar	23.7	773
	Hydro	13.2	430
	Battery storage	1.8	58
	Biomass	1.4	45

Figure 7: Ancillary service categories in Mainland China [26].

ation control and automatic power control), peak shaving, reserve service, system inertia, and ramping service. Automatic voltage control and phase modulation are two reactive power balancing services implemented to ensure voltage stability. Meanwhile, contingency and restoration services are designed to respond to and recover from unexpected disturbances. This category includes black start capabilities and the stable disconnection of generators and loads.

3.2.2 Demand response initiatives

An increasing number of demand response initiatives and projects have been implemented in Hong Kong and Mainland China to explore effective business models for engaging distributed flexibilities in grid power balancing. These projects primarily focus on peak shaving. Some examples include:

- *CLP's Peak Demand Response Programme in Hong Kong* [27]:
 - 950,000 households were invited in 2023 to reduce their energy use during peak demand periods on hot summer days.
 - 410 MWh of electricity was saved over a 4-hour peak time, equivalent to a 160-ton reduction in carbon emissions.
- *Virtual power plant pilot project of State Grid Jibei Electric Power Company* [28]:
 - 35 users and 156 flexible resources were involved, including electric heating with storages, industrial and commercial flexible loads, smart homes, energy storages, electric vehicle charging stations, and distributed PVs.
 - A maximum response capacity of 154 MW was achieved in 2022, with a peak shaving rate of 15 MW/minute.
 - Continuous peak shaving services have been provided for over 5,225 hours since 2019.
- *Shenzhen Public building demand response project of China Southern Power Grid* (ongoing):
 - Aggregating over 100 public building load terminals to achieve a flexibility capacity exceeding 10 MW.

Case Study II highlights recent energy-flexible building developments in China's Greater Bay Area.

Case Study II: Energy-Flexible Building Development in China's Greater Bay Area

The development of energy-flexible buildings in subtropical high-density cities could greatly benefit the energy transition of power systems due to their large power con-

sumption. Effective and generic technologies are being explored for the widespread development and implementation of energy-flexible buildings. Some examples include:

1. *International Gateway Centre project of Sun Hung Kai Properties*: This project aims to develop Hong Kong's first mega smart building with both energy-flexible and energy-efficient features. The building, with a total floor area of 300,000 m², is expected to be completed in 2025. Implementing demand-limiting control of HVAC systems and bio-diesel generators reduced peak demand by 5.3%, saving HK\$0.6 million in operating costs.
2. *"Future Complex" project of Shenzhen Institute of Building Research [29]*: This demonstration project concerns a "Photovoltaic-Energy Storage-Direct Current-Flexibility" system in Shenzhen, covering a gross floor area of 62,523 m². Controlling the energy storage and air conditioning systems achieved a peak reduction ratio of 51.6% and 50%, respectively.

4 Technologies and Strategies to Drive Building Energy Efficiency and Grid Support Services

We can utilise many established and emerging technologies to drive greater provision of grid support services from buildings and improve their energy efficiency. Smart sensors, loads and inverters, artificial intelligence (AI), and advanced building materials are some of the main novel technological innovations being applied in this area.

4.1 Smart sensors

Smart sensors collect, interpret, and process real-time environmental and operational building data, typically within an Internet of Things (IoT) platform [30]. As such, they often contain wireless connectivity, enabling remote monitoring and control, bringing about an enhanced level of awareness and control that can help influence decision-making and improve operational efficiency. We can leverage the increased visibility of a building's energy usage as part of demand response initiatives to maximise resource flexibility and feed this data to an energy management system (EMS) to optimise the building's devices.

Examples of smart sensors include [30]:

- **Gas and air quality sensors:** that measure air quality and can be used to alter a space's ventilation.
- **Temperature sensors:** that measure ambient air temperature and are used to determine whether a space needs to be heated or cooled.
- **Humidity sensors:** that measure the air moisture levels for users' comfort.
- **Motion or occupancy sensors:** that determine whether a space is occupied—we can develop usage patterns and volume trends from the resulting data, informing decision-making or control policies.

4.2 Smart loads and inverters

Smart energy conversion systems are another technology we can leverage to exploit building load flexibility for demand response provision. For example, smart loads are controllable devices or appliances that provide real-time access to their energy usage data, are controllable from an energy management perspective, and are energy efficient [31], [32]. Such loads are a critical enabling technology for smart buildings since they facilitate information exchange between each other and control devices [33]. The information furnished can include a load's properties, status, or external control commands. Examples of such loads include:

- **Smart appliances** like washing machines, dishwashers, or dryers that intelligently operate during off-peak times.
- **HVAC systems** that adjust according to weather fluctuations or building users' occupancy patterns [34].
- **Smart EV chargers** that can optimise the charging process based on renewable energy, the time of day, or grid conditions [35].
- **Data Centres** based on buildings are becoming a significant load, and they are equipped with various power electronic converters. If they are intelligently managed, they can provide flexibility services to the power grid.

Smart inverters are another critical technology, particularly for integrating solar PV and

BESSs at the distribution level [36]. These inverters provide enhanced functionality to support the grid, such as:

- **Frequency and voltage regulation:** Facilitating active and reactive power control.
- **Fault ride-through:** Allows the inverter to stay connected to the grid during disturbances.
- **Remote monitoring and control:** Provides better visibility to grid operators and utilities and can help with aspects of real-time control.

4.3 Artificial intelligence and machine learning

AI generally refers to using “intelligent machines” to solve problems [37]. Machine learning (ML) is a subfield of AI where we combine data and algorithms to train a model that allows it to make predictions or decisions using new data [38]. Over time, with greater exposure to data and feedback on their previous performance, ML algorithms “learn” and adjust how they process data over time.

Smart buildings’ extensive data generation (see the previous subsection on smart sensors) provides an ideal environment for deploying these tools. We can thus leverage AI and ML tools to enhance smart building grid support provision [39]–[41].

Some of the benefits associated with AI and ML applications in smart buildings include [42]:

- **Data-driven decision-making:** We can leverage advanced data analytics to make informed decisions using real-time and historical data.
- **Predictive capabilities:** We can leverage historical trends to predict future outcomes, informing optimal control policies that help maximise the participation of building resources in demand response initiatives.
- **Adaptability and learning:** ML algorithms are inherently adaptable and continually learning, ensuring high future performance.
- **Integration with other technologies:** AI and ML inherently integrate with and complement the ubiquitous IoT technology in smart buildings.

Table 4: Summary of energy retrofit types and measures

Retrofit Type	Measures	Examples
Passive Retrofitting	Enhancing the thermal envelope to reduce heating/cooling demand	Wall/roof insulation, double or triple glazing, improved airtightness, green roofs, external shading, ventilated façades
Active Retrofitting	Improving the efficiency of energy systems and appliances	High-efficiency HVAC systems, condensing boilers, LED lighting, mechanical ventilation with heat recovery, building automation and control systems
Renewable Retrofitting	On-site renewable energy integration to supply clean energy	Rooftop PV panels, solar water heating, geothermal heat pumps, small-scale wind turbines

4.4 Retrofit strategies for energy-efficient buildings

Building retrofitting refers to the process of upgrading existing structures to enhance their energy performance, reduce environmental impacts, and extend their useful life. By 2040, existing buildings will comprise nearly two-thirds of the global stock [43]. Thus, targeted energy-efficiency interventions in these buildings are critical to limit emissions and support global climate goals. As the bulk of the global building stock predates modern energy standards, retrofitting represents a pragmatic, resource-efficient, and a sustainable approach to enhance energy performance without full-scale reconstruction. Building retrofitting strategies can be broadly categorised into passive, active, and renewable measures, each contributing differently to energy efficiency and flexibility [44]. Table 4 summarises those key measures with examples, highlighting the diverse pathways through which retrofitting supports the transition towards energy-efficient buildings.

4.4.1 Retrofitting Leading to Energy Efficiency, Energy Flexibility, and Grid Support Services

Energy efficiency refers to the ability to maintain comfort and functionality while minimising energy use via reduced losses, optimised systems, and clean energy integration. By systematically reducing demand, optimising system performance, and integrating clean energy supply, retrofitting directly translates into measurable improvements in energy efficiency at both the building and system levels. For instance:

- RACE (reliable affordable clean energy) for 2030 reports that upgrades in existing Australian homes could lower household energy use by 30-50% and reduce costs by 20-40%, equating to average annual savings of \$400-600 per poorly performing home [45].
- By 2015, China's National Energy Retrofit Program (ongoing) had upgraded 990 million m² of residential floor area in northern heating zones, benefiting over 15 million households, while significantly improving thermal comfort in aging buildings and delivering annual savings of 6.5 million tonnes of standard coal [46].
- The World Bank-supported Green Energy for Low-carbon City Project retrofitted 67 buildings in Shanghai's Changning District, delivering annual savings of ~78,083 tonnes and cutting CO₂ emissions by ~189,946 tonnes [47].

However, modern energy systems are expected to deliver both efficiency and flexibility. Retrofitted buildings contribute to this via integrating technologies like smart thermostats, high-efficiency heat pumps, and thermal storage, which enable temporal load shifting. Well-insulated homes can pre-heat or pre-cool during periods of high renewable generation and maintain comfort during peak hours with minimal additional demand. HVAC systems equipped with smart controls can dynamically adjust operation to reduce grid stress. Through these capabilities, retrofitted buildings evolve into active nodes of energy management, facilitating demand response and improving grid stability. Figure 8 illustrates the pathway from building retrofitting to enhanced grid support services.

4.4.2 Barriers and Future Considerations

While building retrofits offer significant potential for improving energy performance and sustainability, their implementation faces various challenges. Most existing studies are

Figure 8: Framework linking building retrofitting, efficiency, flexibility, and grid support services.

concentrated in developed regions, limiting the generalisability of findings to other geographic and socio-economic contexts. Financial constraints, such as high upfront costs and slow returns on investment, often discourage implementation. Furthermore, the absence of robust policy frameworks and insufficient stakeholder awareness or technical expertise hinder effective decision-making. Practical limitations, including incomplete architectural data, structural constraints in existing or heritage buildings, and a lack of integrated, multi-dimensional evaluation methods, introduce uncertainties in projecting retrofit outcomes and limit strategic planning [48].

Looking ahead, future retrofit strategies must adopt a multidimensional perspective, assessing retrofit impacts not only on energy efficiency but also on indoor environmental quality (thermal comfort, air quality, acoustics, and lighting). Economic evaluations must include lifecycle costing, return on investment, and sensitivity analyses under varying market conditions. Expanding the scope from individual buildings to district-level retrofits can enhance regional energy performance and sustainability outcomes. Additionally, future studies should utilise high-resolution, measurement-based models to minimise technical and financial uncertainties. The integration of multi-criteria decision analysis and Life

Figure 9: Barriers and future considerations for building retrofits aiming energy efficiency.

Cycle Assessment (LCA), along with consideration of user behaviour, policy support, and climate adaptation, is essential for developing context-specific and scalable retrofit strategies. Figure 9 summarises the barriers to future considerations pathways to building retrofit projects.

4.5 Building material advancements

Solar façades integrate unique solar panels directly into a building’s façade, maximising its power generation capacity [49]. While not related to load flexibility, this technology could enhance a building’s overall energy flexibility and its prosumer⁸ characteristics. When used with BESSs, we can store excess electricity generation for grid support service provision.

Advanced insulation materials can also significantly improve building energy efficiency, enhancing thermal performance that consistently maintains indoor temperature and reduces the need for heating and cooling. Better insulation also improves user comfort

⁸Recall that the term “prosumer” is commonly used to describe distributed energy resources that act as both electricity consumers (loads) and producers (generators).

in other ways, such as reducing ambient noise. Some innovative insulation materials include [50]:

- **Aerogels:** Extremely lightweight, with a low thermal conductivity that can be used in walls, roofs, and windows to provide superior insulation.
- **Phase change materials:** Absorb and release thermal energy during phase transitions and can be integrated into walls, floors, and ceilings.
- **Vacuum insulation panels:** Comprise a core material encased in a vacuum-sealed envelope that provides high thermal resistance. They are ideal for thin walls, floors, and retrofitting projects with limited space.

5 Opportunities to Support the Grid via Building Loads

The confluence of new technologies and ancillary service markets provides various opportunities to support the grid via building loads, which we touch upon in this section.

5.1 Capability and applicability of building load flexibility for different grid storage needs

Integrating intermittent and uncontrollable renewable energy sources requires significant investment in energy storage to maintain generation-demand balance and reliably operate power systems. The storage needs span various timescales, including:

1. Short-term and high-frequency storage from seconds to 30 minutes
2. Medium-term storage from 30 minutes to 4 hours
3. Long-term storage from 4 hours to a few days
4. Super long-term and seasonal storage from weeks to seasons

Building load flexibility has recently been recognised as a cost-effective alternative for facilitating high renewable penetration since it can function as short-term, medium-term, and long-term storage, contributing to grid power balancing under high renewable energy penetration.

5.2 Applicability of building load flexibility for current ancillary services

Currently, peak shaving is the only permitted ancillary service building participants can provide in Mainland China. This service can rapidly curtail building loads within 60 seconds. The flexibility resources include building integrated combined heat and power (CHP)/combined cooling, heating, and power (CCHP), electrical energy storage systems, and air conditioning or heating systems. For example, air conditioning or heating systems can be temporarily curtailed by shutting down chillers/heaters, resetting indoor temperature etc., without significantly affecting occupants' thermal comfort. Buildings with relatively large consumption can participate directly in the market. Small consumers can be grouped or integrated with other distributed resources by load aggregators and virtual power plants to provide at least the minimum required flexibility capacity within a specified time.

5.3 Potential opportunities of building load flexibility for power grid balancing

Building load flexibility also has significant potential to contribute to primary and secondary frequency regulation control and reserve services. This potential has been recognised in ancillary services markets in countries like the United States (US). The frequency regulation service can be provided by adjusting buildings' variable frequency drives in response to frequency deviations, swiftly changing power consumption. The flexibility resources include building integrated electrical energy storage systems, variable speed fans, variable speed compressors, variable speed pumps and dimmable lighting systems. In the event of a sudden generation loss or demand spike, we can curtail building loads and respond within 10 to 30 minutes for reserve services. For example, HVAC systems can be pre-cooled or pre-heated during off-peak periods to provide up reserve service.

The capacity of building load flexibility to provide these ancillary services is significant. In Hong Kong, existing HVAC systems in the commercial building sector can provide 80 MW of flexibility for frequency regulation, meeting 50% of the current grid requirement. Additionally, they can offer 600 MW of flexibility for spinning reserve, satisfying over 70% of the current grid requirement [51].

5.4 Barriers to building load flexibility adoption and deployment

Various barriers must be addressed to facilitate large-scale adoption and deployment of building load flexibility for ancillary service provision. This includes providing proper incentives for building owners, ensuring interoperable communication infrastructure, adopting effective and easy-to-implement control strategies, and addressing concerns about data privacy when aggregating building load flexibility.

Upgrading building and air-conditioning controls to enable building-grid interaction is particularly essential. Smart sensor deployment underpins these upgrades by providing real-time data on building occupancy, temperature, humidity, and other environmental factors. These devices must be integrated with a building automation system that uses sophisticated algorithms to analyse data and make informed decisions about air-conditioning operations. By continuously monitoring and adjusting the air-conditioning systems, the building automation system ensures that the building load patterns can respond to grid signals.

Another key feature of this upgrade is the ability to participate in demand response programs. The building automation system should be able to automatically adjust air-conditioning settings in response to signals from the grid. The system should be capable of integrating data from various sources, including IoT sensors, weather forecasts, and energy market signals. Incorporating machine learning capabilities for the control system to analyse historical and real-time data is also necessary.

6 Regulatory and Policy Landscapes

The evolving nature of power systems and demand response programs worldwide means the regulatory and policy landscapes are also continuously evolving and, in most cases, trying to keep up with the pace of change.

6.1 The Australian context

In Australia, the former Council of Australian Governments Energy Council (COAG EC) tasked the Energy Security Board (ESB) to advise on the required NEM design changes as the power system transitions further to variable renewable energy generation [52].

The ESB's resulting Post 2025 market design has sought to unlock choices and more significant value for consumers in the future by [53]:

- **Developing more flexible trading arrangements** that separate management generation and load from the uncontrollable energy supply to homes and businesses, removing barriers and making it easier for smaller players to engage with the market.
- **Reforming trader services** that will cut out red tape by creating a single universal registration category for all entities who want to do business in wholesale energy and services.
- **Reforming scheduled lite** to encourage smaller players like aggregators managing direct load control or local community batteries to voluntarily give information concerning decentralised generation size, availability, and operation to AEMO for managing the supply-demand balance.
- **Ensuring consumer protections are fit-for-purpose**, allowing consumers to safely try different products and switch between providers if they wish to do so.
- **Evolving the roles and responsibilities** for traders (aggregators/retailers), distribution networks, and the system and market operator.

In December 2024, the Australian Energy Market Commission (AEMC) released a final determination introducing reform that allows virtual power plants, commercial and industrial demand response, and aggregated batteries to compete directly with large-scale generators in the energy market [54]. Further developments are likely to occur and should be considered when implementing demand response programs. In general, numerous regulatory and policy issues need to be addressed as part of demand response programs, including market participation and design, data privacy and security, interoperability standards, energy accessibility and equity, and consumer protections. Some standards and provisions that influence the practical implementation of demand response in Australia are discussed below.

6.1.1 AS/NZS 4755.1:2017 - Demand Response Capabilities and Supporting Technologies for Electrical Products

This standard intends to support demand response programs that optimise the electricity supply's operation and allow the efficient planning and use of capital equipment while minimising the risks to the comfort and amenities of electrical products' users [55]. The standard does this by:

1. Creating a framework that allows off-the-shelf equipment, communications technologies, and electrical products to be integrated and adapted so that demand management solutions may be developed and deployed in a timely and economical manner.
2. Specifying the minimum functionality of a demand response enabling device.
3. Describing additional, optional functionalities that a demand response enabling device may incorporate.
4. Describing various means of communicating with a remote agent which qualifies demand response enabling devices to be designated as distinct classes.

6.1.2 Green Star Buildings

The Green Star building rating system evaluates the environmental performance and sustainability of the built environment [56]. Green Star Buildings v1.1 is currently under consultation. If the proposed changes are ratified, demand response will become more significant [57]. Some of the proposed requirements include:

- *The Zero Carbon Action Plan must be done before the tender phase of the project...The plan must also outline, if relevant any additional capacity built into the building, substations, or building systems to enable any proposed changes. This may include the capacity to accommodate any future additional loads, energy storage or demand response solutions that may occur or be implemented during the life of the building.*
- *The building has real-time energy management and information systems that set up the building to be grid interactive. As a minimum, this includes...ability to ingest*

data relating to the local electricity network's greenhouse gas emissions intensity and operating demand to allow for an appropriate and timely demand response.

- *At the time of commissioning of the building, a report is generated that clearly defines the building's flexibility characteristics and is provided to the electricity retailer responsible for supplying electricity to the building premises. As a minimum, the report includes the...rated full load power consumption of the heating and cooling systems present in the building, and measured power reduction resulting from implementing one or more demand response strategies:*

6.1.3 Other rating systems and provisions

Other rating systems and provisions that influence the built environment include:

- The **National Construction Code (NCC)**, which is Australia's primary set of technical design and construction provisions for buildings, provides a performance-based code that sets the minimum required level for the safety, health, amenity, accessibility and sustainability of certain buildings [58].
- The **Nationwide House Energy Rating Scheme (NatHERS)**, which provides energy ratings for new dwellings and provides a streamlined pathway to meet or exceed the new NCC 2022 energy efficiency requirements [59].
- **NABERS Energy rating**, which is an independent rating system that is based on real energy data and provides a comparison between similar buildings across the built environment, including, but not limited to, office buildings, apartment buildings, shopping centres, hotels, schools, and hospitals [60].

6.2 The Hong Kong and Mainland China context

Compared to the relatively comprehensive regulations established in countries like the US, Hong Kong and Mainland China lag significantly behind. However, in recent years, Mainland China has increasingly recognised the importance of building load flexibility in enhancing grid reliability and efficiency. As a result, increasing efforts have been made to develop more comprehensive policies to integrate demand response and load flexibility into its grid management strategies.

Hong Kong has gradually implemented demand-side management measures to enhance energy efficiency and grid stability. The on-peak demand charge pricing tariff (\$/kVA) has been adopted for several years. CLP Power Hong Kong Limited promotes smart meter use and peak demand management programs to encourage customers to reduce the load during peak hours. Furthermore, the Scheme of Control Agreements with power companies also encompasses incentives for renewable energy and energy efficiency initiatives. However, currently, direct regulations or policies specifically addressing building load flexibility engagement in grid support ancillary services are not yet fully developed.

In Mainland China, the government has shown a strong commitment to demand response and load flexibility. The National Energy Administration and the National Development and Reform Commission have released several guidelines and policies to promote demand response. This includes the *Demand Response Management Measures (Trial)*, *14th Five-Year Plan: Modern Energy System Planning (2021-2025)*, and the *Southern Regional Power Ancillary Services Management Implementation Rules*. These policies encourage buildings to participate in demand response programs and to provide grid ancillary services. It is important to note that China is divided into several grid regions, each with its own operator and potentially different rules for demand response and load flexibility.

While considerable progress has been made in promoting load flexibility, particularly in Mainland China, the complexity of integrating these resources into grid operations means that policy development remains an ongoing process. Buildings in Hong Kong have higher power consumption and well-established building automation systems, offering greater energy flexibility with higher controllability compared to those in Mainland China. These flexible resources can benefit local grid management and facilitate high renewable penetration in Mainland China. However, this potential has not been well recognised by the Hong Kong government. Effective regulations, policies and market mechanisms are essential to utilise building load flexibility effectively in Hong Kong.

7 Future Research and Industry Questions

A range of open questions currently exist related to grid support service provision from smart buildings, some of which we pose below.

7.1 Open industry questions

1. What are the most attractive financial opportunities for smart buildings to participate in grid support services across Australia, Hong Kong, and Mainland China?
2. What load technology balance (e.g., HVAC, EVs, etc.) provides the most harmonious and equitable demand response across these geographical locations?
3. How can ancillary service markets be best designed or structured for the above load technology balance?
4. How can we best apply AI, ML, or other algorithms to capitalise on the above opportunities?
5. What are the main hurdles to significantly leveraging smart buildings for grid support service provision in Australia, Hong Kong, and Mainland China?
6. How receptive are building owners or occupiers to participating in demand response in Australia?

7.2 Open research questions

1. How can we best leverage and apply AI and ML for smart buildings' provision of grid support services?
2. What alternative algorithms or control paradigms could we employ for smart building grid support services, and how might AI and ML enhance them?
3. What do techno-economic analyses identify as the most suitable loads or technologies to leverage under the current and future ancillary service market designs in Australia, Hong Kong, and Mainland China?

8 Conclusion

This paper has examined demand response service provision to the power grid via smart building load flexibility. Initially, we introduced building energy flexibility and how a load's power adjustments can be characterised by their direction, electrical capacity, resource availability and predictability, and response time. We then introduced three (3) main

building energy flexibility categories: shiftable loads like washing machines and EVs, non-shiftable loads such as lighting and cooking appliances, and other controllable loads like HVAC systems and water heaters. The main opportunities we identified for exploiting load flexibility in buildings centred upon HVAC systems, EVs, and hot water systems. HVAC systems are attractive given their abundance, power usage, and availability. Meanwhile, EVs are highly flexible—particularly those with V2G technology. Hot water systems have different response characteristics to HVAC systems and EVs and thus may be beneficial for providing various demand responses.

We also discussed power grid support services and demand response initiatives across Australia, Hong Kong, and Mainland China. Australia has a mature ancillary service market structure, particularly concerning frequency control. Numerous demand response initiatives have been completed, and others are underway. Meanwhile, Mainland China is in the early stages of developing a comprehensive ancillary services market. Hong Kong's ancillary service structure is less mature than Australia's. The Australian initiatives could serve as a valuable reference for implementing building load flexibility in Hong Kong.

We then analysed critical emerging technologies for grid support service provision. The interplay between smart sensors, AI, and ML represents a significant opportunity to improve decision-making, adaptability, and flexibility. Solar façades are promising for potentially improving buildings' prosumer characteristics. Building flexibility that can function as short-term, medium-term, and longer-term storage will be necessary for power grid balancing with high penetrations of renewable energy. We will also need to continually refine our regulatory and policy frameworks as new technologies arise that facilitate further smart building grid support service provision. Last, we posed a range of open industry- and research-focused questions that currently exist.

9 References

- [1] F. Milano, F. Dörfler, G. Hug, D. J. Hill and G. Verbič, 'Foundations and challenges of low-inertia systems (invited paper),' in *2018 Power Systems Computation Conference (PSCC)*, 2018, pp. 1–25. DOI: 10.23919/PSCC.2018.8450880.

- [2] X. Liang, 'Emerging power quality challenges due to integration of renewable energy sources,' *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 53, no. 2, pp. 855–866, 2017. DOI: 10.1109/TIA.2016.2626253.
- [3] V. Natarajan and G. Weiss, 'Synchronverters with better stability due to virtual inductors, virtual capacitors, and anti-windup,' *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 64, no. 7, pp. 5994–6004, 2017. DOI: 10.1109/TIE.2017.2674611.
- [4] International Energy Agency, 'World energy outlook 2023,' 2023.
- [5] International Energy Agency, *World energy outlook 2023 free dataset*, data retrieved from International Energy Agency, <https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/data-product/world-energy-outlook-2023-free-dataset-2#data-sets>, 2023.
- [6] Y. G. Rebours, D. S. Kirschen, M. Trotignon and S. Rossignol, 'A survey of frequency and voltage control ancillary services—Part I: Technical features,' *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 350–357, 2007. DOI: 10.1109/TPWRS.2006.888963.
- [7] S. A. Hosseini, M. Toulabi, A. Ashouri-Zadeh and A. M. Ranjbar, 'Battery energy storage systems and demand response applied to power system frequency control,' *International Journal of Electrical Power Energy Systems*, vol. 136, p. 107 680, 2022, ISSN: 0142-0615. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2021.107680>.
- [8] J. Morren, S. de Haan, W. Kling and J. Ferreira, 'Wind turbines emulating inertia and supporting primary frequency control,' *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 433–434, 2006. DOI: 10.1109/TPWRS.2005.861956.
- [9] I. Mahmud, N.-A. Masood and A. Jawad, 'Optimal deloading of PV power plants for frequency control: A techno-economic assessment,' *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 221, p. 109 457, 2023, ISSN: 0378-7796. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsr.2023.109457>.
- [10] P. Palensky and D. Dietrich, 'Demand side management: Demand response, intelligent energy systems, and smart loads,' *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 381–388, 2011. DOI: 10.1109/TII.2011.2158841.
- [11] L. Silvestri and M. De Santis, 'Renewable-based load shifting system for demand response to enhance energy-economic-environmental performance of industrial enterprises,' *Applied Energy*, vol. 358, p. 122 562, 2024, ISSN: 0306-2619. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.122562>.

- [12] Australian Government - Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water, *Commercial buildings*, <https://www.dcceew.gov.au/energy/energy-efficiency/buildings/commercial-buildings#:~:text=The%20commercial%20building%20sector%20is,lower%20energy%20bills>, Accessed: 2024-09-13, 2024.
- [13] Australian Government - Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water, *Residential buildings*, <https://www.dcceew.gov.au/energy/energy-efficiency/buildings/residential-buildings>, Accessed: 2024-09-13, 2024.
- [14] International Energy Agency, 'Characterization of energy flexibility in buildings,' Tech. Rep., Dec. 2019.
- [15] C. Eid, P. Codani, Y. Chen, Y. Perez and R. Hakvoort, 'Aggregation of demand side flexibility in a smart grid: A review for European market design,' in *2015 12th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM)*, 2015, pp. 1–5. DOI: 10.1109/EEM.2015.7216712.
- [16] F. Plaum, R. Ahmadiyahangar, A. Rosin and J. Kilter, 'Aggregated demand-side energy flexibility: A comprehensive review on characterization, forecasting and market prospects,' *Energy Reports*, vol. 8, pp. 9344–9362, 2022, ISSN: 2352-4847. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyr.2022.07.038>.
- [17] Australian Energy Market Operator, *The National Electricity Market*, <https://aemo.com.au/-/media/files/electricity/nem/national-electricity-market-fact-sheet.pdf>, Accessed: 2024-10-21, 2024.
- [18] Australian Energy Market Operator, *Guide to Ancillary Services in the National Electricity Market*, https://aemo.com.au/-/media/files/electricity/nem/security_and_reliability/ancillary_services/guide-to-ancillary-services-in-the-national-electricity-market.pdf, Accessed: 2024-10-14, 2023.
- [19] Australian Renewable Energy Agency, *AGL Demand Response*, <https://arena.gov.au/projects/agl-demand-response/>, Accessed: 2024-09-30, 2021.
- [20] Australian Renewable Energy Agency, *PLUS ES South Australia Demand Flexibility Trial*, <https://arena.gov.au/projects/plus-es-south-australia-demand-flexibility-trial/>, Accessed: 2024-09-30, 2023.
- [21] Australian Renewable Energy Agency, *Enel X Commercial Refrigeration Flexible Demand Project*, <https://arena.gov.au/projects/enel-x-commercial-refrigeration-flexible-demand-project/>, Accessed: 2024-09-30, 2023.

- [22] Australian Renewable Energy Agency, *Realising Electric Vehicle-to-Grid Services*, <https://arena.gov.au/projects/realising-electric-vehicle-to-grid-services/>, Accessed: 2024-10-01, 2023.
- [23] Hong Kong Government, 'Hong Kong's Climate Action Plan 2050,' Hong Kong Government, 2021.
- [24] China Government - National Energy Administration, <https://www.nea.gov.cn/2024-10/31>, Accessed: 2024-11-13.
- [25] CLP Power Hong Kong Limited, *Peak Demand Management*, <https://www.clp.com.hk/en/business/low-carbon-solutions/energy-management/peak-demand-management>, Accessed: 2024-11-09.
- [26] Southern Regulatory Bureau of the National Energy Administration, 'Southern Regional Power Ancillary Services Management Implementation Rules,' National Energy Administration, 2022.
- [27] CLP Power Hong Kong Limited, *2023 Sustainability Report - Case Studies*, <https://sustainability.clpgroup.com/en/2023/case-studies/case-study/case-study-auto-grid-enables-clp-s-peak-demand-response-programme-to-achieve-global-gold-standard>, Accessed: 2024-11-09, 2023.
- [28] State Grid Jibei Electric Power Company, <https://www.jibei.sgcc.com.cn/>, Accessed: 2024-11-09, 2023.
- [29] Committee of Photovoltaic Energy Storage, Direct Current and Flexibility, *Case Studies of Photovoltaic-Energy Storage-Direct Current-Flexibility*, 2023.
- [30] Verkada, *Guide to IoT Smart Sensors*, <https://info.verkada.com/smart-buildings/iot-smart-sensors/>, Accessed: 2024-09-14, 2024.
- [31] A. Ahmad and J. Y. Khan, 'Optimal sizing and management of distributed energy resources in smart buildings,' *Energy*, vol. 244, p. 123 110, 2022, ISSN: 0360-5442. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2022.123110>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544222000135>.
- [32] G. Chandra Mahato, S. Ranjan Biswal, T. Roy Choudhury, B. Nayak and S. Bikash Santra, 'Review of active power control techniques considering the impact of MPPT and FPPT during high PV penetration,' *Solar Energy*, vol. 251, pp. 404–419, 2023, ISSN: 0038-092X. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2023.01.035>.
- [33] G. Benetti, D. Caprino, M. L. Della Vedova and T. Facchinetti, 'Electric load management approaches for peak load reduction: A systematic literature review

- and state of the art,' *Sustainable Cities and Society*, vol. 20, pp. 124–141, 2016, ISSN: 2210-6707. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2015.05.002>.
- [34] Air-rite, *Upgrading to smart HVAC systems: Benefits for commercial properties*, <https://www.airritemech.com.au/upgrading-to-smart-hvac-systems-benefits-for-commercial-properties/>, Accessed: 2024-12-19, Nov. 2024.
- [35] EVSE, *Smart EV chargers*, <https://evse.com.au/smart-ev-charging/?srsltid=AfmBOor2Cjfc3SO2pZA5ZAUc6v1gPg6SQSgz19dXzXOGTyiXK1ufMr0J>, Accessed: 2024-12-19, 2024.
- [36] Interstate Renewable Energy Council, *Smart inverters*, <https://irecusa.org/our-work/smart-inverters/>, Accessed: 2024-12-19, 2024.
- [37] IBM, *What is artificial intelligence (AI)?* <https://www.ibm.com/topics/artificial-intelligence>, Accessed: 2024-09-14, 2024.
- [38] Sara Brown, *Machine learning, explained*, <https://mitsloan.mit.edu/ideas-made-to-matter/machine-learning-explained>, Accessed: 2024-11-14, Massachusetts Institute of Technology - Sloan School of Management, Apr. 2021.
- [39] E. Mocanu, P. H. Nguyen, M. Gibescu and W. L. Kling, 'Deep learning for estimating building energy consumption,' *Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks*, vol. 6, pp. 91–99, 2016. DOI: 10.1016/j.segan.2016.02.005.
- [40] E. Mocanu, D. C. Mocanu, P. H. Nguyen *et al.*, 'On-line building energy optimization using deep reinforcement learning,' *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 3698–3708, 2019. DOI: 10.1109/TSG.2018.2834219.
- [41] Y. Wang, Y. Tang, Y. Xu and Y. Xu, 'A distributed control scheme of thermostatically controlled loads for the building-microgrid community,' *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 350–360, 2020. DOI: 10.1109/TSTE.2019.2891072.
- [42] Smart Spaces, *AI: Driving the Future of Smart Buildings*, <https://www.smartspaces.app/blog/ai-driving-the-future-of-smart-buildings/>, Accessed: 2024-09-14, 2024.
- [43] M. A. Aloshan, 'Achieving near-zero energy in hot climates: Retrofitting building envelopes for existing homes,' *Heliyon*, vol. 11, no. 3, e42170, 2025, ISSN: 2405-8440. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2025.e42170>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S240584402500550X>.

- [44] M. Ibrahim, F. Harkouss, P. Biwole, F. Fardoun and S. Ouldboukhitine, 'Building retrofitting towards net zero energy: A review,' *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 322, p. 114 707, 2024, ISSN: 0378-7788. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2024.114707>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378778824008235>.
- [45] R. Raven and L. Smith, 'Energy upgrades for australian homes,' RACE for 2030 CRC, Tech. Rep., Oct. 2024.
- [46] S. Lu, W. Feng, X. Kong and Y. Wu, 'Analysis and case studies of residential heat metering and energy-efficiency retrofits in china's northern heating region,' *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, vol. 38, pp. 765–774, Oct. 2014. DOI: 10.1016/j.rser.2014.07.015.
- [47] Y. Xiangqing, *Supporting low-carbon city development in shanghai*, <https://www.worldbank.org/en/results/2020/10/12/supporting-low-carbon-city-development-in-shanghai#>, Accessed: 2025-09-14, 2020.
- [48] C. Citadini de Oliveira, I. Catão Martins Vaz and E. Ghisi, 'Retrofit strategies to improve energy efficiency in buildings: An integrative review,' *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 321, p. 114 624, 2024, ISSN: 0378-7788. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2024.114624>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378778824007400>.
- [49] Metsolar, *BIPV facade systems*, <https://metsolar.eu/products/bipv-facade-systems/>, Accessed: 2024-09-14, 2024.
- [50] ibeam, *Advanced insulation materials: Revolutionizing energy efficiency in modern architecture*, <https://ibeam.ae/advanced-insulation-materials-revolutionizing-energy-efficiency-in-modern-architecture/>, Accessed: 2024-12-17, Jul. 2024.
- [51] H. Wang, S. Wang and R. Tang, 'Development of grid-responsive buildings: Opportunities, challenges, capabilities and applications of hvac systems in non-residential buildings in providing ancillary services by fast demand responses to smart grids,' *Applied Energy*, vol. 250, pp. 697–712, 2019, ISSN: 0306-2619. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.04.159>.
- [52] Energy Security Board, 'Post-2025 Market Design Final advice to Energy Ministers Part A,' Tech. Rep., Jul. 2021.
- [53] Energy Security Board, 'Clean and Smart Power in the New Energy System,' Tech. Rep., Jul. 2021.

- [54] A. E. M. Commission, *Energy market gets clear vision: Reform opens door for all to benefit from virtual power plants*, https://www.aemc.gov.au/news-centre/media-releases/energy-market-gets-clear-vision-reform-opens-door-all-benefit-virtual-power-plants?utm_source=LinkedIn&utm_medium=social&utm_campaign=VPPs, Accessed: 2024-12-19, Dec. 2024.
- [55] Standards Australia and Standards New Zealand, 'AS/NZS 4755.1:2017 Demand response capabilities and supporting technologies for electrical products,' Tech. Rep., Mar. 2017.
- [56] Green Building Council of Australia, *A rating tool for new buildings and major refurbishments*, <https://new.gbca.org.au/green-star/rating-system/buildings/>, Accessed: 2024-11-15, 2024.
- [57] Green Building Council of Australia, 'Green Star Buildings v1.1: Consultation on Proposed Changes,' Tech. Rep., 2024.
- [58] National Construction Code, *Introduction to the National Construction Code (NCC)*, <https://ncc.abcb.gov.au/editions/ncc-2022/adopted/volume-one/preface/introduction-national-construction-code-ncc>, Accessed: 2024-11-15, 2022.
- [59] Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water, *About NatHERS*, <https://www.nathers.gov.au>, Accessed: 2024-11-15, 2024.
- [60] NABERS, *NABERS Energy*, <https://www.nabers.gov.au/ratings/our-ratings/nabers-energy>, Accessed: 2024-11-15, 2024.

